

ISic2927

I.Sicily inscription 2927

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Memo[ria]

1a. (vac.unknown)

2. Ianua

3. rii d(omni) n(ostri) Gen

4. tionis [servi]

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1993 (which is after Bernabò Brea 1947) with slight changes based on Manganaro's apograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645311

Bibliography

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Agnello, S.L. 1950. Iscrizioni cristiane di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 26: 221-222. At 222 no.9

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.

Vatican. At no.347

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio.*

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 585 no.7 fig.27

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